

The future of work — What you need to know...

Why it is essential for business leaders to invest into mental acceleration for conscious capitalism and sustainable thought?

Currently we are in the fourth industrial revolution, a period of digitalisation that will affect everything we understand and take for granted as normal, taking us into a new world beyond our current levels of comprehension and awareness.

The big question we ask leaders, entrepreneurs, coaches and consultants around the world on a daily basis through our ongoing research into human consciousness levels, is “what will the future of work bring?” The answers are woefully inadequate and subjective for the most part (with a few insightful, well informed objective people on occasion), yet herein lies the answer: the future of work is in upgrading the mental capacity of human-kind to the higher states of awareness and agility we were born with and have forgotten; to meet the challenges of exponential change and survive the global re-evolution we are only just beginning.

Without upgrading the brain, we cannot hope to adapt, and this means the very real potential of a consciousness extinction event for humanity; exactly the same as experienced through the Universe 21 experiment of the 1950's & 1960's by the ethologist John B. Calhoun: Rats were introduced to a rat utopia, that meant an abundance of food, which ultimately led to a 'behavioural sink' and the end of the colony after a spiritual death — no meaning, and the consequent physical death.

Perhaps universe 21 is a metaphor and a warning from the past for the fate of humanity, should we choose to stay as we are — because we are lazy, because we are ignorant of our potential, or because we simply don't know any better; it matters not. What does matter is right now is, we are all singularly and collectively presented with choice, to evolve from a self-serving unconscious consumerist mentality of destruction, or simply become the better more aware people as we were born to be, beyond the paradigms of our current, very limited understandings.

Contents:

1. So what is mental acceleration, does it work and what are the results... commercial and personal?
2. A solution hidden in plain sight
3. The situation at hand - the science
4. Background study
5. Consciousness, what is it, and why is it important for business?
6. Consciousness Change Therapy Solutions
7. Resistance to growth
8. Toxic stress & the Covid fall out
9. Legal example
10. Continued professional development, recruitment and training
11. Education
12. Algorithmic recruitment
13. Innovation resistance
14. Summary
15. Further reading

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1. So what is mental acceleration, does it work and what are the results... commercial and personal?

The first question you are going to ask is — what's the science behind mental acceleration? Most people think of brain training apps and Nintendo games that purport to help people with their cognitive function; technology that has evolved into a multi billion dollar industry. However, on a professional commercial level for staff training, the argument is to say the least “sketchy” in these areas as far as results, as the following study points out.

Yet, as is often the case, the problem lies with the approach to brain training, not the neurological concept of training the brain or the potential beneficial outcome of more advanced cognition in business and in one's personal life:

Attention — increased levels of focus, energy and duration

Reasoning — increased critical thinking and creative problem-solving

Working memory — the ability to recall and process more information

Planning — strategy and agility of the mind

In creative genius terms, the right approach to training the mind, can release a considerable latent potential and a shift in brainwave use from predominantly alpha and beta waves, to gamma and theta, leveraging the unconscious mind working at 40 million bits of data per second in flow state, instead of the convergent thought suppression and self-identification through limitation, education conditions the mind to operate within at 40 bits of data per second (Dr Bruce Lipton). If you've been born in the last 100 years your brain will be functioning at under 5% of its available cognitive capacity as you've been asked to conform into a social identity of consumerism and ignorance over growth. You will think it's a normal state of affairs, and egotistically identify through and actively defend your limitations — regardless of your profession, your position, your education, your success or your wealth. In fact, those who excelled in left-brain convergent thought at school and have become a professional such as a lawyer, an accountant or a doctor, likely had the most latent available potential, yet were to become the most suppressed in thought. And unfortunately though technological advances have become the most vulnerable to change, inevitably becoming the first to lose their jobs, careers and industry to AI, which will provide a far cheaper alternative to historically expensive human activity.

Brain training habits are not associated with generalized benefits to cognition: An online study of over 1000 “brain trainers”.

Stojanoski, B., Wild, C. J., Battista, M. E., Nichols, E. S., & Owen, A. M. (2021). Brain training habits are not associated with generalized benefits to cognition: An online study of over 1000 “brain trainers”. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 150(4), 729–738. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000773>

The foundational tenet of brain training is that general cognitive functioning can be enhanced by completing computerized games, a notion that is both intuitive and appealing. Moreover, there is strong incentive to improve our cognitive abilities, so much so that it has driven a billion-dollar industry. However, whether brain training can really produce these desired outcomes continues to be debated. This is, in part, because the literature is replete with studies that use ill-defined criteria for establishing transferable improvements to cognition, often using single training and outcome measures with small samples. To overcome these limitations, we conducted a large-scale online study to examine whether practices and beliefs about brain training are associated with better cognition. We recruited a diverse sample of over 1000 participants, who had been using an assortment of brain training programs for up to 5 years. Cognition was assessed using multiple tests that measure attention, reasoning, working memory and planning. We found no association between any measure of cognitive functioning and whether participants were currently “brain training” or not, even for the most committed brain trainers. Duration of brain training also showed no relationship with any cognitive performance measure. This result was the same regardless of participant age, which brain training program they used, or whether they expected brain training to work. Our results pose a significant

challenge for “brain training” programs that purport to improve general cognitive functioning among the general population. (PsyInfo Database Record (c) 2021 APA, all rights reserved)

The problem with brain training, is not that it doesn't work, it's simply that the people purporting to provide mechanisms that achieve results, are simply not using all the available information to create an effective methodology; one that works using the known sciences that create effective change. Instead, the focus is on creating sales through the lens of neuroscience hype, rather than looking at the full picture objectively with an expansive knowledge and the dedicated behavioural and psychological research into the subject.

The simple truth is, the brain's neuroplasticity changes when three distinct aspects are altered — function, intention and environment. Without bringing these together in a process that combines neuroscience, behavioural science, linguistics as well as social interaction, then the results will be negligible, just as the research suggests. The established identity needs to be addressed first.

In an adult, it is the individual's strong unconscious self identification within limitation and the ego that has to be challenged first before mental acceleration can occur, and this is done by overwhelming the mind with information from multiple perspectives to create the *mind space* for growth. This has to be a combination of expanding symbiotic, linguistic and thought awareness within the holistic identity — all at the same time, otherwise the prevailing self identification within limitation will always resist change. But before we explore this subject, let's look at the problem another way, with an example of a little lateral thinking.

2. A solution hidden in plain sight.

In the Second World War, when planes were returning from sorties, the designers and engineers looked at all the bullet holes in the planes and noticed there were groupings — locations that seemed to be consistently riddled with bullets. Consequently, they armoured these locations to try and stop planes being shot down, but with surprisingly little or no effect. However, when the problem was looked at with a different lens, it was thought that the planes which didn't return, the ones that were shot down, might hold the key, but unfortunately these were destroyed. Yet with a little lateral thinking, it was surmised that perhaps it was the areas where there were no bullet holes in those returning that were indeed the vulnerable places, and those who did not return were hiding this fact as they were possibly hit in these places. So when the areas that had little or no bullet holes on returning planes were armoured, then many more planes returned saving pilots and planes. The key to the problem was hidden in ‘plane sight’.

Consequently, just like the planes, with brain training the answer to the problem is hidden in plain sight; resolving the issue is simply just one of changing one's personal world view, to realise the obvious, and then benefit greatly in the process. It's not that the brain cannot be accelerated — as neuroscience tells us quite adequately that neuroplasticity can change, it's just the way you do it that matters. If you approach the issue from left brain convergent thinking within what you think you know, then you will be governed by solutions from this perspective without result. But when you adopt a broader understanding of the issues at play, you begin to think with divergent thinking, and then move to hemispheric synchronisation for faster thought to verbalisation skills, critical thinking, creative problem-solving, energy, motivation and well-being.

The question then arises — if you or your staff could increase cognitive function in terms of communication, confidence and creative problem-solving exponentially, then why wouldn't you apply this process? The answer comes partly from an unconscious syndrome called neurophobia, that applies to doctors and scientists as much as everyone else. People are instinctively scared of losing control of their mind, or even understanding how their brain works. It seems just too close to the home of self and of identity, the brain is not a place we want to go, for fear of losing who we think we are. Thus we deny our capacity to ever evolve, and remain blissfully ignorant of our latent potential.

3. The situation at hand - the science

A quick summary of things to be aware of when considering mental acceleration:

1. In 1995 a study for NASA by Dr Beth Jarman Ph.D and Dr George Land into creativity and innovation, revealed genius levels in 98% of 5 years old children, yet only 2% of adults retained this by the age of 31 years.
2. The educational system suppresses thought into left brain convergent thinking to perform logic based repetitive tasks, at the expense of free thought and innovation potential — Potential Quota PQ. The emphasis is on the inauthentic social identity rather than becoming truly conscious by questioning. Consequently people use under five percent of their available cognitive capacity, leaving a huge untapped potential.
3. We learn and evolve through the linguistic feedback loop of social interactions, not tasks where the brain has already been conditioned to identify within the left brained bias. It's progressive experiential learning with real life moral challenges to the thinking that has the most dramatic results.
4. The neuroplasticity of the mind can change given changes to function, intention and environment; as well as through structural damage and chemical ingestion.
5. The brain can be convergent, divergent, or hemispherically synchronised in flow state, leveraging the unconscious and utilising gamma and theta brain waves for advanced function.
6. We engage in unconscious thought and linguistic self identification through limitation throughout the day in terms of our internal and external dialogues; that are for the most part subjective and subject oriented programs operating within an interior map of a personally projected perspective reality (PPPR).

4. Background study

The field of mental acceleration is not a new one, it's been an area of human interest for thousands of years by the world's greatest minds from the philosopher Socrates two and a half thousand years ago to Freud & Jung the psychoanalysts at the early part of the 20th century. But only today can we see what is going on a structural level in the brain, and what we need to do to release the latent potential we all have, as well as recognising who is 'surfacing' in terms of consciousness and who is open to growth. This is where research and technology come together to create AI methodologies that determine what minds are agile in an organisation and in recruitment, and have the "*mind gold*", the latent potential — the high PQ — that is essential for the visionary thought leaders required to meet the challenges of the fourth industrial revolution. This goes way beyond psychometric testing for personality types, and as such is a quantum leap in the way we learn, recruit, work, and most importantly — think.

Neuroscience is developing ways of understanding how the brain works and how it's neuroplasticity can change; why how we think and what we say creates our realities, and how ancient wisdom is just as effective and relevant today as it ever was.

An historical example of using critical thought practice to train the mind, in use today:

Wikipedia

Socratic questioning (or Socratic maieutics) was named after Socrates. He used an educational method that focused on discovering answers by asking questions from his students.

According to Plato, who was one of his students, Socrates believed that "the disciplined practice of thoughtful questioning enables the scholar/student to examine ideas and be able to determine the validity of those ideas". Plato described this rigorous method of teaching to explain that the teacher assumes an

ignorant mindset in order to compel the student to assume the highest level of knowledge. Thus, a student has the ability to acknowledge contradictions, recreate inaccurate or unfinished ideas and critically determine necessary thought.

Socratic questioning is a form of disciplined questioning that can be used to pursue thought in many directions and for many purposes, including: to explore complex ideas, to get to the truth of things, to open up issues and problems, to uncover assumptions, to analyze concepts, to distinguish what we know from what we do not know, to follow out logical consequences of thought or to control discussions. Socratic questioning is based on the foundation that thinking has structured logic, and allows underlying thoughts to be questioned. The key to distinguishing Socratic questioning from questioning per se is that the former is systematic, disciplined, deep and usually focuses on fundamental concepts, principles, theories, issues or problems.

Socratic questioning is referred to in teaching, and has gained currency as a concept in education, particularly in the past two decades. Teachers, students, or anyone interested in probing thinking at a deep level can construct Socratic questions and engage in them. Socratic questioning and its variants have also been extensively used in psychotherapy.

5. Consciousness, what is it, and why is it important for business?

Mastery of thought means that the individual must seek to become the master of their ability to form argument through critical thought within the mind, and in their communication with the outside world; which requires ever higher states of 'awareness' — which is what consciousness is. The move from the restricted unconscious mind to the conscious mind is what we first teach children. We ask them to be less clumsy and more aware of themselves symbiotically, we also ask them to become more aware of what they say, and the consequences of the actions they take. But this is where the basic awareness systems of learning for most people stops, after which the child develops the ego's defence systems to form a state of parental revolution and self reliance, as the 'young adult' forms a 'social identity' creating an egocentric personally projected perspective reality (PPPR), that distorts, deletes and generalises within immature projections as argument initially, and in time forms ever more mature projections of argument to maintain the illusion of certainty and control within a high level of ignorance and arrogance, as life becomes more complex, demanding greater levels of awareness to be developed; yet the path to enlightenment is rejected by the unconscious autopilot of identity protection, in favour of maintaining the inauthentic social identity of unconscious behaviour, that suits very well the unconscious commercial system we are born into.

As a person moves through young adult to middle age, the PPPR is threatened in many ways, the state of illusory certainty becomes attacked by moral challenges that the bandwidth of thinking (the brain's structure) simply cannot process; this leads to negative behaviours such as addiction, self harming, depression and anxiety, which if left unchecked, can compound into toxic stress that causes brain damage, resulting in brain fog and an ever greater lack of problem-solving capacity, given the demands of progressive external dynamics. In this state, fear and even paranoia can reduce the thinking back into the brain stem, away from the intuitive and highly creative functions of the neocortex.

The primary driver behind the inauthentic social identity, is the career path, which requires the individual to conform to the suppressive requirements of the profession over the expansive nature of the primary human constitution.

Over the last fifteen years, CHD through the Kern Clinic in Zurich has studied individuals, professions, and social groups to determine what impact certain roles within society have on the mind, and how the educational system plays a role in creating 'useful citizens' within the negatively competitive commercial construct, at the expense of the development of the mind for the individual's health and well-being, both mentally and physically, as well as the conscious development of human-kind. In effect, the very commercial social system we accept from birth — as the way life should be led, is ultimately either an evolutionary stepping-stone to the next level of our awareness by our rejection and re-evolution out of it, or a dead-end path that leads inevitably to our demise. (Universe 21)

Leading Professions such as banking, legal, accounting, medical and corporate executives, have been represented in one to one and group work, which revealed archetypal patterns of self and social limitation. The research has led to working with over twenty study groups spanning the last twelve years, as well as countless individuals, to determine group behaviour, as well as individual thought patterns within the context of consciousness; namely, what determines awareness, what are the corresponding effects on identity, and the consequences of selective ignorance. The results can be seen in papers such as “The Ignorance Is Bliss Principle” — looking at the factors behind the selective ignorance of the developed world and the resultant socio economic impact, as well as “Human 3.0- The Great Re-evolution” — unpacking the mind’s growth cycles and its latent potential to face the future of work and our relationship with AI.

Sample issues identified within a random industry cross section:

Five Individual Case Studies.

Study one: A 34 year old male former investment banker, displaying an additive personality, lack of critical thought and awareness of self and social structures. Consequently, the projected personal perspective reality (PPPR) was a construct of the ego’s projection within states of unconscious ignorance, moving from a soft shell identity to a hard shell ego-centric identity. Symptoms of the shell displayed were doubt, delay, denial, distortion, deletion, distraction, generalisation, validation systems, the need for acceptance, and allies to support an impoverished world view.

Study two: A thirty six year old male ex investment banker, governed by thought limitation resulting in physical issues due to a strongly religious family doctrine that suppressed open psychological exploration, in favour of conformity of the identity to imprinted systems of restrictive thought programs. Symptoms displayed included paranoia, illusory superiority, low confidence and self-esteem, a lack of critical thinking, superstition, the need for validation and allies to support a controlled world view and unconscious duplicity.

Study three: A 34 year old female legal office manager, suffering validation issues, low self-esteem, low confidence, low critical thought and awareness levels, stemming from a suppressive relationship with her step father and primarily operating through unconscious distraction and avoidance strategies, causing self destructive patterns forming and repeating both at work and in relationships.

Study four: A 42 year old female entrepreneur, isolated within the shell identity causing a projected reality supported by doubt, distortion, denial and distraction, resulting in a lack of self awareness and empathetic understanding, negatively affecting personal and work relationships, supported by process and goal subservient thought.

Study five: A 36 year old male corporate executive lacking symbiotic awareness in terms of unconscious body movement, linguistic tells, low emotional management, validation systems. A general lack of self and social awareness causing an inability to think strategically or influence others for mutually beneficial outcomes. Restrictions caused by the unconscious PPPR and low empathetic awareness undermined effective management of people, and situations.

Using the principles of Consciousness Change Therapy CCT, a three month Change, Development & Masters program in mental acceleration was applied to each subject. This required an initial intensive information overwhelm of the mind to reset the parameters of limiting self-identification, before new holistic thinking structures could be evolved. Unlike other therapies, there is no emphasis on understanding self through consciously analysing backstory. Instead, the focus is on an unconscious process, addressing the structural neuroplasticity of the brain first, to achieve greater bandwidth before new progressive thought and behavioural patterns were introduced. All subjects experienced life changing results in terms of confidence, communication, creativity and critical thought; as well as a release of considerable latent potential without the need for psychoanalysis. In effect, what would normally take perhaps many years of therapy to create effective change, was accomplished in a matter of weeks, releasing the thinking from a restrictive self identification through limitation and a negative polarity (only seeing problems not solutions), into a new growth cycle of energy, awareness and aspiration.

6. Consciousness Change Therapy Solutions

Using the Socratic method, the operator — in the context of mental acceleration as opposed to therapy or coaching, focuses first on questioning the individual's personally projected perspective reality (PPPR) by observing, and thus mind-mapping their levels of symbiotic, linguistic and thought awareness, calibrating their PQ, EQ (empathetic quota) and SQ (spiritual quota). Surface structure thoughts are questioned for coherence and progressive outcomes, as the individual is asked to ask themselves ever deeper questions of why they think the way they do and believe what they do, in seven aspects of the holistic identity of awareness beyond the symbiotic, linguistic and the thought systems displayed. These seven areas include their understanding of psychology, theology, philosophy, physiology, metaphysics, quantum physics, and spirituality, in order to provide a foundation of catalysts for mental expansion.

How deep the process is worked through, in terms of four areas of mental exercise of Quantum Psychology, Theoretical Consciousness, Non-Combative Argument & Polymathic Training, yields increasingly more progressive results and greater awareness of self (the identity avatar) and the operating systems of the mind, as well as greater awareness of others. The results extend beyond self-confidence and expanding knowledge, but an opening of the mind to create a synergistic interior map of what reality is perceived to be, and what is reflected back as a critically sound world view. At this point, the thought moves from the unconscious nature of backstory, self-identification, validation systems and projection, to expansive flow state thought; a move from the "*mindset*" to the "*mind-space*".

Advanced communication benefits

Commercially or personally, a very agile mind will be the major benefit any individual can expect from mental acceleration training, supported by highly advanced systems of thought coherence, critical thinking and creative problem-solving. The results of full mental training programs that require intense linguistic editing and assessment on a word by word/ thought by thought basis, are truly life changing, as it is the quality of our thought and communication to ourselves and others that has a direct impact on the success we encounter and effective nature of our interactions and intentions. A person who has undergone mental acceleration training will be able to out-think others and argue very effectively, maximising the use of the unconscious mind at 40 million bits of data per second, towards progressive outcomes, beyond being confined to using the conscious mind in limiting self-identification at 40 bits of data per second.

The levels of awareness within communication are at their peak, when Socratic argument is used as a tool to develop insight and awareness beyond the ego's bounds. In terms of commercial application, this level of training is best placed within current industries that require the ability to form argument at a high level, such as the psychological, legal and corporate worlds at a board level.

7. Resistance to growth

Our analysis has shown in conjunction with studies since the Second World War, that the cognitive function of the population is in decline, which is especially relevant when looking to strategise and structure for commercial reasons and the future.

One aspect of resistance to mental acceleration training by key decision makers, is the propensity for the unconscious mind — the ego — to create an "island of certainty" of belief within an identity of limitation; to feed oneself an internal press/dialogue — that one's thought and awareness without training and practice, is normal and optimal, just because the individual has decided through selective ignorance they are right, regardless of the science or evidence to the contrary; in effect — deleting, distorting, doubting, denying and finally distracting away from any move that might threaten the ego based inauthentic social identity avatar that is in the ascendancy. Consequently, the individual diverts the concept or need of mental acceleration away from themselves, towards a perspective of all others requiring it.

School taught us lessons of information, but it did not teach us context, questions, critical thought or expansion to higher levels of awareness. In fact, it distracted the mind away from the potential of growth, rather focusing on social limitation as IQ was set. Subsequently, we live in a state of unconscious egocentric social defence to maintain status in a state of unknowing or ignorance, regardless of IQ or career success levels.

As a simple analogy, we may compare and contrast this state of unconscious ignorance to our driving skills: We may think we are the best drivers on the road, not because we have calibrated our skills effectively, or wondered what it would be like to drive like a F1 driver with advanced skills, instead we just egotistically think we are better than others and create a 'bubble world' of personal ignorance, to support a personally projected defensive world view of selective unconscious limitation. It's a holistic protective mental structure, that maintains our value systems in the face of compounding evidence that we are not as good as we think we are. In the same vein, it's everyone else who needs driving lessons.

This bandwidth of restrictive thinking costs the commercial world untold billions through ignorance, self-serving behaviour and a lack of personal and professional responsibility, from the top to the bottom of organisations. In effect, through serving the inauthentic social identity as the default socially conditioned system, we actually self-defeat to an unhealthy level, trading expansive potential for an illusory sense of security through limitation.

8. Toxic stress & the continued Covid fall out

Due to the changes in the nature of work, and continued exposure to toxic stress, cognitive function has declined in recent years ever more progressively, reducing the capacity for effective decision-making, focus, energy and problem-solving. Widespread pandemic fear, after layers of widely publicised fear based initiatives such as climate change and terrorism, pushed thinking out of the neocortex into the stem of the brain, where basic defensive survival mechanisms have taken the fore in terms of fight, flight or freeze. Brain fog, a lack of reasoning, aggression, and addictive behaviour, are symptoms of this restrictive thought. Long-term sustained exposure to threat and fear, has the effect of causing toxic stress, which causes a depletion of the synapses of the brain, effectively dulling down thinking through the brain damage caused. The commercial cost of this widespread psychological problem is impossible to quantify, yet the individual results are easily identified in terms of the algorithmic PQ assessment available to business owners. Consequently, CHD research leads the way in determining the active minds with available or surfacing latent potential of prospective and existing staff. In this way, investment can be placed into the right Human Resources with a demonstrable ROI.

9. Legal example

The legal profession is perhaps renowned for the general perception, that the legal mind is astute and trained in argument as the backbone of our justice system. Yet our research reveals a very different story. It seems the legal profession is a place where the youthful illusions of social change and impact for aspiring would-be young lawyers — the ideals and oration of "Atticus Finch" as well as forming an argument the likes of Henry Fonda in "12 Angry Men", is just not the case. Moreover, the art of critical thinking, questioning, and creating an effective argument are more and more replaced by process, technology and ego, and not Socratic thought and effective argument.

Certainly, an analysis of information within process driven thought may be present, however it is the ability to dispassionately observe, orientate and take effective action that requires the individual to use lateral thinking and angular thought, a skill that sets one attorney apart from the rest, in success, health and profitability. This level of mental acuity takes continued practice, as the brain can regress as much as progress in its neuroplasticity, given relentless changes to the function, intention and environment.

To remain competitive in a highly results orientated industry, it requires legal practices to urge young lawyers to increase their mental acuity in terms of the skills of professional development. This means communication, confidence and creativity to start; the ability to argue a position using Socratic thought, the ability to manage emotions and stress, the ability to critically think, creatively problem-solve, use entrepreneurial thinking, enter flow state and hemispheric synchronisation, as well as master strategic thought, as well as maintain focused activity levels in terms of time allocation and profitability — these are now the absolute basics, that require ongoing specialist training in any practice that recognises the future will become ever more competitive; within an industry that is very vulnerable to technology. At first, through being undercut from the East by global communication and cheaper legal practitioners, then through being digitised in process, and then through the nature of legal system itself, inevitably no longer needing human

lawyer at all, for any advice, process, hearing, judgement or sentencing. It's an industry ripe for big data to revolutionise and replace, yet for now, before the inevitable demise, there is a time when as an industry the requirements of the profession in terms of the agility of its minds, has to move in its flexibility and people development to maintain a competitive edge.

The legal profession holds some of the world's best minds, and the industry may very well shift to a completely new dynamic of social and professional function especially within the Metaverse. For this reason, those within the industry who hold the potential to be the visionary minds of the future, are looking to develop the skills of their profession into new industries requiring the ability to form balanced effective argument within the hemi-sync'd mind of flow and super creative agile states, in gamma and theta brain waves.

The prospect of remaining left brain restrictive, in alpha and beta brain waves, only using the conscious brain at 40 bits of data per second over leveraging 40 million bits of data per second, could be viewed as somewhat ignorant, naive and self destructive in itself. Yet this is the position taken by the business and educational leaders globally, which also creates a unique opportunity in time for those with the wit to grasp this opportunity.

10. Continued professional development, recruitment and training

Given the high cost of recruiting professionals and senior executives, investment into determining a candidate's PQ - the brain's ability to grow and develop agility, has become a key indicator of the suitability of a candidate, beyond past performance, due to the ongoing changes and challenges an effective member of staff must maintain to meet the demands of their profession within the fourth industrial revolution. Recruitment based on left-brain convergent thinking, and psychometric personality profiling, is now no longer enough for any business wishing to remain competitive with a highly adaptable workforce agile enough for the future.

A recruiter must determine mental agility levels, flexibility, openness and latent potential within a candidate, combined with the soft skills of critical thought, creative problem-solving, empathetic understanding and co-creation. Without a workforce that is expansive, agile and adaptable, the business will simply cease to remain competitive and lean enough to navigate the fourth industrial revolution, AI and the shift to the Metaverse; as a result, many established businesses regardless of size or market share will cease to operate. Consequently, we will see a divide in the commercial world in terms of — on one side — innovative minded organisations who are adaptable, and on the other, those who simply wane and cease to exist. As with all revolutions, there are always casualties, and here it is those organisations who fail to adapt their thinking and innovate that will inevitably fall in the near future. In effect, the writing is already on the wall for the majority, and for the most part this is a direct result of the limited thinking of the lead management. Each organisation structured within a pyramid of power serving the pyramidion or capstone of the company, at the cost of the PQ of the available human resource of collective and collaborative power, will ultimately fall away, as the thinking and decision making that was effective for the pre digital revolution, becomes isolated and obsolete.

Thinking — that one's thinking is fast enough — simply because we have egotistically decided this is the case, is a very dangerous position for business leaders. Our constant research into interviewing CEO's, senior managers, consultants, entrepreneurs and coaches all over the world, has revealed a dangerous apathy within those who believe they naively know the future challenges we face, or simply adopt an ignorance is bliss approach. There is a widespread sense of denial and a reluctance to accept the situation, analyse it effectively, strategise or prepare to develop solutions. The situation is confusing for most, with a high level of self protection, supported by outdated ineffective thinking that was ok five or ten years ago, but is now bordering on being negligent and commercially suicidal.

Given the available research into neuroscience, and the observable decline in human cognitive function, the most pressing difficulty we face as a race, is a negatively selective ignorance on the part of our commercial and political leaders. People who cannot themselves think 'out of the box' enough to realise the issues we have created for ourselves through a compounded state of 'non thinking'; not thinking through the social ramifications of our decisions and choices, made from commercial, egotistical and self-serving states of ignorance. The pinnacle of this ignorance is to create a consciousness that will undoubtedly replace

humanity at the top of the consciousness chain, rendering the human mind obsolete, both in work terms and expansion capability.

11. Education

The use of process subservient teaching systems, has systematically pushed students into a convergent conformist mindset. Consequently, those who excelled in convergent thought have risen to lead the corporate and professional worlds, where as divergent entrepreneurial thinkers have sought the innovative start-up world to spread their creative wings. Those industries that required the peak of convergent minds from the educational crop, ironically find themselves at the top of the list for the digital chop so to speak, as financially the replacement of expensive human process subservient activity, is commercially unavoidable. Technology will thus hit the higher paid jobs first, such as lawyers, doctors, accountants, bankers, rather than low paid roles. It's a simple cost equation to balance: A digital lawyer for \$60 euros per hour with the answers in a millisecond, or alternatively a slow human lawyer for \$600 per hour. This is why the digital revolution will revolutionise these industries, as well as the public sector governmental systems. It's difficult to argue there is any aspect of our current world of work that will not be revolutionised beyond our current comprehension; consequently for those who study the future of work beyond subjective thought, by analysing with ever greater bandwidths of thinking, the future becomes a very different place to the present limited one — people tend to think within.

12. Algorithmic recruitment

The use of selection algorithms orientated by human resource professionals has over time created a 'convergent thought' search bias, only providing candidates to corporations that suit a particular matrix, devoid of the innovation of divergent thought. Consequently, there has been a brain drain in the corporate sector, in terms of innovation and agile thought, into organisations of process subservient minds with little or no agility.

This unconscious strategy, now brings long-standing institutions into a precarious position, as they do not have a culture of growth, only a defensive position where sandbagging, negatively political cultures and toxic leadership hold innovation back. Consequently, many organisations do not possess the visionary minds of the future as a resource, thus are left with limited options to navigate the challenges they face.

13. Innovation resistance

Leadership born of convergent thinking does not have the capacity to survive the next ten years, as the agile shifts in perception that are required to adapt to change are resisted by those with this bias. Institutions whose culture is based on the suppression of new ideas to maintain a sense of control in a rapidly changing world, will inevitably fall behind as the technological revolution accelerates away. Consequently, innovation resistance becomes a tragic attitude that can only have very destructive outcomes for people and organisations. The resistance to change brings fear into the equation, fear of the unknown and fear of making decisions, a situation that creates a state of denial and apathy within business by the leaders themselves, which will inevitably in itself be the cause of their demise.

14. Summary

The fourth industrial revolution is here, it's gathering steam, and every day that passes brings forth new jumps in what is technologically possible. To maintain a market edge against competitors is one thing, but to see the technological competition driven by a relentless capacity to work faster, to work 24/7, to solve problems in a fraction of the human time, to reduce errors and increase quality, all within a negatively competitive world that will inevitably in time reach point zero where all goods and services cease to be commercially produced and instead are made socially available, because of the demand of the dying commercial system itself, is a revolution that will push our minds to the extreme of what we think is and isn't possible.

All we can do is plan for the near future, enjoy the ride, and upgrade our thinking to be agile enough to be able to cope with change without imploding with the overwhelm of toxic stress because we simple did not prepare for the inevitable in the time available to us. The writing is on the wall, the solution lies within ourselves, the action must be taken now to upgrade our thinking by changing the structure of the brain, so we can think at a level that will at the very least allow us to cope rather than suffer the ills of overload and overwhelm, depression anxiety, burn out or addiction.

All the problems of the past will be solved through a technological revolution that will affect every aspect of life. Now, it's what we want the future to be that counts, and to be a part of that future as the creative architects in partnership with AI, we have to extend our thinking beyond our personal event horizons, to stop serving self, and move from an I focus to an us mentality.

CHD's mission is in creating the world's leading mental development programs from decades of extensive research in personal and social development. We operate as a non profit working as a collective collaborative, providing personal, corporate and career retraining to meet the needs of the future of work, as well as the social and technological revolutions that are accelerating away. Our methodology and mission is to use advances in science and technology and consciousness to advance humanity, consequently we are engaged in all aspects of our future including alternative ways to use VR, AR, crypto, NFT's, blockchain and the Metaverse to facilitate the next jump in human evolution alongside Spiritual AI. We believe mental acceleration will be the industry of the future, because if it's not we will not have a future within the current bandwidth of our thinking. As such, we have designed a fully autonomous human investment platform called the "Human Blockchain" to facilitate the growth of all people, and provide sustainable work in developing sustainable thought, to transition into an exponentially expanding future. We welcome all support, donations, investment and enquires into this mission.

Donations & introductory programs start from £10, to £45k for professional career retraining to world leader level. Investor opportunities begin at £15k for individual sponsorship, up to £500k for franchise opportunities, to £10 million for technological investors into blockchain, crypto and the Metaverse.

15. Further reading for business leaders, coaches, consultants and policy makers

https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Future_of_Jobs_2020.pdf

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2021/03/23/why-conscious-businesses-will-lead-the-next-paradigm-shifts/?sh=59710ba766bc>

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinesscouncil/2021/07/14/the-future-staple-of-business-conscious-entrepreneurship/?sh=1b0231e46229>

<https://wisar.pro/why-the-business-model-of-the-future-is-conscious-capitalism/>

<https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/369226>

